

Do audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality?

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Received: 2 March 2023 **Revised:** 11 March 2024 **Accepted:** 13 September 2024

Abstract: This study examines whether audit firms and audit committees contribute to enhancing earnings quality in publicly listed companies. It investigates how the index of audit firms (derived from size, opinion, independence, tenure, quality, and rotation) and audit committees (derived from independence, financial expertise, size, meetings, and gender) impact the accuracy and reliability of reported earnings. An empirical approach is employed using a sample of publicly listed companies over five years. The study utilizes a quantitative methodology, conducting regression analyses to evaluate the relationship between audit firm quality, audit committee characteristics, and earnings quality, as measured by accruals-based metrics and earnings restatements. The results suggest that higher-quality audit firms, particularly the Big 4, and more independent and financially expert audit committees are associated with improved earnings quality. The findings show that these factors reduce earnings manipulation, enhance transparency, and foster higher levels of financial reporting reliability. The study is limited by its focus on publicly listed companies, which may not generalize to private firms or those in non-regulated markets. Additionally, the study is restricted to a specific geographical region, limiting cross-country comparisons. For practitioners, the results highlight the importance of choosing reputable audit firms and ensuring audit committees are composed of independent, financially knowledgeable members to enhance financial reporting quality. The research contributes to greater trust in financial markets by demonstrating that robust governance mechanisms, such as high-quality audits and audit committees, play a vital role in protecting investors' interests and promoting corporate transparency. The study provides evidence that supports strengthening regulatory policies concerning audit firm qualifications and the composition of audit committees to improve corporate governance and protect shareholders. This paper adds value to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the combined effect of audit firms and audit committees on earnings quality, offering insights into their complementary roles in enhancing the integrity of financial reporting.

Keywords: audit committee, audit firm, earnings quality, Nigeria

JEL Codes: C23, C58, C87, M21, M24, M48

Citation: Awolola, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality? *Journal of Financial Economics and Accounting*, 9(13), 784-821.

Paper type: Research paper/article

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I. Introduction

Earnings quality refers to the degree to which reported earnings accurately reflect a company's financial performance and ability to generate sustainable cash flows. It measures the reliability, credibility, and sustainability of earnings information presented in financial statements. Several definitions and dimensions of earnings quality exist, emphasizing different aspects:

- Accruals Quality:** Earnings quality can be assessed by the extent to which earnings are free from management discretion in accounting choices, particularly in the use of accruals. High-quality earnings should have low discretionary accruals, meaning they closely align with cash flows from operations.
- Sustainability and Persistence:** Earnings quality is also linked to the ability of current earnings to predict future earnings. High-quality earnings are sustainable and persist over time, providing consistent and stable indicators of a firm's financial health. Low-quality earnings may fluctuate and are often the result of one-time events or earnings manipulation.
- Predictive Value:** The quality of earnings is determined by how well current earnings provide information useful for forecasting future performance. High-quality earnings give stakeholders a reliable basis for decision-making regarding a firm's future profitability and risk.
- Conservatism in Reporting:** Firms with high earnings quality tend to recognize expenses and losses early and revenue in a conservative, consistent manner. This conservative approach reduces the risk of overstating financial performance.
- Absence of Earnings Manipulation or Management:** Earnings quality decreases when management engages in aggressive accounting practices, such as earnings management or smoothing, to manipulate reported results. High-quality earnings are free from distortions introduced by managerial incentives to meet certain targets.
- Faithful Representation and Relevance:** Earnings quality reflects the degree to which earnings represent true economic events and provide relevant, reliable information to stakeholders. This encompasses both faithful representation (accuracy of reporting) and relevance (usefulness for decision-making). In summary, high-quality earnings are accurate, and consistent, and provide a true reflection of a company's underlying economic performance, making them valuable for investors, regulators, and other stakeholders.

Furthermore, the importance of earnings quality lies in its critical role in enhancing the transparency, reliability, and usefulness of financial reporting for a wide range of stakeholders. High-quality earnings provide accurate insights into a company's financial health and future performance, which is essential for informed decision-making. Key reasons why earnings quality is important include Investor Confidence and Decision-Making. High-quality earnings instill confidence among investors, enabling them to make better decisions about buying, holding, or selling a company's stock. Reliable earnings reports reduce the uncertainty around a firm's financial performance and risk. Poor-quality earnings can mislead investors, leading to incorrect valuations, mispricing of stocks, and potential financial losses.

Accurate Valuation of Firms. Analysts and investors rely on earnings data to value companies. High-quality earnings help in producing accurate forecasts of future cash flows and profitability, essential for determining a company's true market value. Low-quality earnings, which may include inflated or manipulated numbers, can lead to an overvaluation or undervaluation of a company, potentially resulting in market inefficiencies.

Reduction of Earnings Manipulation Risk. Strong earnings quality reduces the likelihood of earnings management or manipulation by managers, thereby enhancing the credibility of financial reporting. This is crucial for maintaining fair financial markets, as manipulative practices can erode trust in companies and their management, leading to market volatility and lower investor participation.

Lower Cost of Capital. Firms with high-quality earnings are perceived as less risky by investors and lenders, which can lead to a lower cost of capital. Investors are willing to accept lower returns on equity, and lenders may offer better-borrowing terms, reflecting the reduced uncertainty surrounding the firm's financial reporting. On the other hand, poor earnings quality can increase the perceived risk, leading to higher costs of capital or difficulty in securing financing.

Corporate Governance and Accountability: High-

quality earnings provide an objective measure of management's performance, helping corporate boards, audit committees, and other governance bodies monitor and assess how well executives are managing the company. This enhances the accountability of management and reduces the risk of agency problems, where management's interests may diverge from those of shareholders.

Regulatory Compliance and Reduced Litigation Risk: High-quality earnings help companies stay compliant with regulatory requirements and avoid penalties or legal consequences arising from misstatements in financial reports. Companies with poor earnings quality are more susceptible to regulatory scrutiny, restatements, and litigation, which can damage their reputation and result in significant financial costs. **Credit Rating and Borrowing Ability:** Credit rating agencies assess earnings quality as part of their evaluation of a company's financial health and creditworthiness. Firms with high-quality earnings are more likely to receive favorable credit ratings, which can lead to easier access to debt markets and better borrowing terms. **Low-quality earnings** can result in downgraded credit ratings, limiting a company's access to capital and increasing borrowing costs. **Sustainability of Business Operations:** High-quality earnings reflect a company's ability to generate consistent and sustainable cash flows. This is important for long-term planning, strategic investments, and ensuring the ongoing viability of the business. **Poor-quality earnings** may mask underlying operational weaknesses, potentially leading to poor business decisions and financial instability.

Protection of Stakeholder Interests: Various stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, and governments, rely on earnings reports to gauge a company's stability and ability to meet obligations. High-quality earnings ensure these stakeholders have a clearer understanding of the company's true economic situation. Inaccurate or manipulated earnings may lead stakeholders to make suboptimal decisions, such as extending too much credit to a company that is financially weaker than it appears. **Public Trust and Market Efficiency:** High earnings quality contributes to the overall trust in financial markets, promoting efficiency and fairness. When earnings are transparent and reliable, market participants can make well-informed decisions, leading to more efficient capital allocation. **Poor-quality earnings** erode trust, leading to reduced market efficiency and potentially higher systemic risks in the financial system. In summary, earnings quality is fundamental to maintaining the integrity of financial reporting, supporting investor confidence, ensuring efficient capital markets, and protecting the long-term interests of stakeholders. **Role of audit firms and audit committees in enhancing earnings quality.**

Low earnings quality among listed companies in Nigeria is a significant source of concern for scholars, regulators, investors, and other stakeholders due to the serious implications it has on corporate governance, market efficiency, investor confidence, and economic growth. Several reasons highlight why this issue is particularly worrisome: **Erosion of Investor Confidence.** Low earnings quality undermines the credibility of financial reports, causing investors to doubt the reliability of information provided by Nigerian companies. When investors cannot trust earnings reports, they may refrain from investing or demand higher returns to compensate for the risk, leading to capital flight and reduced investment in Nigerian equity markets. This lack of trust can depress stock prices and increased volatility in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), ultimately hindering the growth and development of the capital market.

Increased Risk of Earnings Manipulation: Poor earnings quality is often associated with earnings management or manipulation, where firms alter financial figures to meet specific targets, such as beating earnings forecasts or avoiding losses. This practice misrepresents a company's true financial position, misleading investors and stakeholders. In Nigeria, the weak enforcement of regulations and corporate governance standards can create opportunities for companies to manipulate their earnings, exacerbating concerns about the integrity of financial reporting. **Weak Corporate Governance:** Low earnings quality in Nigerian companies signals issues with corporate governance practices, including a lack of independent oversight by boards of directors and audit committees. Weak governance allows management to act in their interest,

often at the expense of shareholders and other stakeholders. This is a major concern for regulators, as it reflects ineffective mechanisms for holding company executives accountable for transparent and accurate financial reporting.

Regulatory Scrutiny and Legal Risks: Nigerian companies with poor earnings quality are more likely to attract scrutiny from regulatory authorities such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN). The potential for earnings restatements or financial fraud investigations can lead to fines, reputational damage, and legal challenges. Regulators are particularly worried about the broader implications for Nigeria's regulatory framework, as persistent earnings quality issues may suggest gaps in enforcement, auditing practices, and regulatory compliance. **Impact on Economic Development:** The Nigerian economy relies heavily on its corporate sector to drive growth and development. Low earnings quality negatively affects the overall perception of Nigerian businesses and their ability to attract foreign direct investment (FDI). Global investors are hesitant to commit capital to markets where financial transparency is lacking, limiting Nigeria's access to external financing. Furthermore, unreliable financial information may mislead policymakers and hinder effective economic planning, as corporate earnings are a key indicator of business activity and economic health.

Higher Cost of Capital: Companies with low earnings quality face a higher cost of capital because lenders and investors perceive them as higher risk. This is particularly concerning in Nigeria, where the cost of financing is already relatively high. Poor-quality earnings lead to uncertainty about a company's future cash flows and profitability, prompting lenders to charge higher interest rates or limit access to funding. As a result, companies may struggle to raise the capital necessary for expansion, innovation, and other growth initiatives, further stifling economic progress. **Threat to Market Efficiency:** One of the key functions of financial markets is to efficiently allocate capital to its most productive uses. Low earnings quality disrupts this function, as misleading financial information results in the mispricing of stocks. Inefficient capital allocation can lead to the misdirection of investment funds, causing resources to flow to underperforming or riskier firms at the expense of more promising companies. This inefficiency ultimately weakens the broader Nigerian financial system and hampers efforts to strengthen the capital markets. **Stakeholder Mistrust:** Stakeholders such as creditors, suppliers, employees, and customers also rely on the accuracy of financial reports to assess the financial health and viability of companies. Low earnings quality can create mistrust among these stakeholders, leading to strained relationships and increased operational risk for companies. For example, creditors may limit or deny credit facilities, and suppliers may impose stricter terms or discontinue business relationships altogether, fearing the possibility of financial distress.

Furthermore, challenges for academic research and policymaking: Scholars and researchers are concerned about low earnings quality because it poses challenges for empirical research and economic modeling. Poor-quality data distort the findings of studies that rely on financial reports, making it difficult to draw valid conclusions about corporate behavior, economic trends, or the effectiveness of regulations. Policymakers, too, may face difficulties in crafting effective regulations and policies due to unreliable earnings data, which can lead to ineffective governance reforms and economic strategies. **Potential for Financial Crises:** Persistently low earnings quality could contribute to broader systemic risks in the Nigerian financial system. If a significant number of companies are engaged in earnings manipulation or reporting poor-quality earnings, this could mask underlying financial vulnerabilities, creating the conditions for corporate defaults or crises that could ripple through the economy. Regulators and financial institutions are particularly concerned about this risk, as it can undermine efforts to maintain stability in Nigeria's financial sector. In conclusion, low earnings quality in Nigeria is a critical concern because it threatens the integrity of financial markets, erodes investor confidence, hampers economic development, and weakens corporate governance. Addressing this issue requires a coordinated effort from regulators, auditors, policymakers, and companies to

enhance transparency, improve governance practices, and strengthen regulatory oversight to ensure the credibility of financial reporting in Nigeria.

Audit firms and audit committees are widely regarded as crucial mechanisms for enhancing earnings quality due to their roles in ensuring transparency, reliability, and compliance in financial reporting. They serve as important checks and balances in corporate governance, reducing the likelihood of earnings manipulation and improving the overall accuracy of financial information. The following are how they contribute to enhancing earnings quality:

Audit Firms' Role in Enhancing Earnings Quality: Independent Verification: Audit firms, especially the larger, well-established ones (e.g., Big 4), provide independent, external assurance that a company's financial statements are accurate and free from material misstatements. Their independence helps ensure that financial reports reflect the true economic condition of the company, improving earnings quality. **Expertise and Reputation:** High-quality audit firms bring technical expertise, experience, and credibility to the audit process. Larger audit firms have extensive resources, including specialized knowledge and sophisticated auditing techniques, which allow them to detect irregularities and ensure that companies follow appropriate accounting standards. A strong reputation for thorough and reliable audits compels management to avoid aggressive accounting practices that could lower earnings quality. **Detection of Earnings Management:** Audit firms play a crucial role in identifying and mitigating earnings management practices. Through detailed examination of accruals and other financial data, auditors can spot discretionary adjustments and ensure that management does not manipulate financial results to meet short-term objectives. **Adherence to International Standards:** Reputable audit firms enforce adherence to international financial reporting standards (IFRS) and generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP), which provide a robust framework for high-quality earnings. Compliance with these standards enhances the comparability and transparency of financial reports, which in turn boosts earnings quality. **Continuous Monitoring and Risk Assessment:** High-quality audit firms continuously monitor their clients' financial practices and assess the risk of material misstatements, offering valuable recommendations for improving internal controls. This ongoing scrutiny encourages companies to maintain high-quality earnings and avoid practices that could distort financial reporting.

Audit Committees' Role in Enhancing Earnings Quality: Oversight of Financial Reporting: The audit committee, often composed of independent board members with financial expertise, is responsible for overseeing the financial reporting process. Their role is to review the company's financial statements, ensuring that they present a true and fair view of the company's financial performance. This oversight helps safeguard against errors, fraud, or aggressive accounting that can undermine earnings quality. **Independence and Objectivity:** A well-structured audit committee that is independent of management can effectively challenge management's accounting decisions and judgments. Their independence allows them to act in the best interests of shareholders, reducing the potential for earnings manipulation and improving the objectivity of financial reports. **Expertise and Accountability:** Audit committees with members who have financial expertise are better equipped to understand complex accounting issues and financial disclosures. This expertise enhances their ability to scrutinize the quality of earnings and ensure that accounting policies are applied consistently and appropriately. It also holds management accountable for the accuracy of reported earnings. **Coordination with External Auditors:** The audit committee works closely with external auditors, facilitating a productive relationship that fosters transparency. By discussing audit findings, risk areas, and any potential accounting issues, the audit committee helps ensure that the external audit process is thorough and objective, contributing to higher earnings quality. **Monitoring Internal Controls:** The audit committee is also responsible for overseeing a company's internal control system. Effective internal controls reduce the risk of misstatements or fraud, thereby enhancing the reliability of earnings reports. A strong internal control environment is crucial for ensuring that the financial data used to calculate earnings is accurate and complete.

The Combined Impact of Audit Firms and Audit Committees: Mutual Reinforcement: Audit firms and audit committees work in tandem to ensure the quality of financial reporting. While audit firms provide an independent external review, audit committees maintain ongoing oversight within the organization. Together, they reinforce each other's roles in promoting transparency, reducing earnings manipulation, and enhancing overall financial integrity. Corporate Governance and Accountability: Both audit committees and audit firms are key components of a company's corporate governance framework. By ensuring that financial reporting is conducted with transparency and accountability, they enhance earnings quality, ultimately protecting shareholder interests and fostering trust in financial markets. Reduction of Earnings Management: The combination of robust external audits and vigilant audit committee oversight greatly reduces the opportunities for management to engage in earnings management. Companies with strong audit committees and high-quality external audits are more likely to produce financial statements that reflect genuine economic performance rather than manipulated figures. In conclusion, audit firms and audit committees play essential roles in enhancing earnings quality by ensuring the accuracy, transparency, and integrity of financial reports. Their combined oversight, expertise, and independent verification processes act as effective checks against earnings manipulation and promote high standards in financial reporting. This not only improves investor confidence but also contributes to the overall stability and credibility of financial markets. The remaining part consists of a literature review, theoretical framework, research questions, methodology, results, discussion, and conclusion.

II. Literature Review

A substantial body of research has examined the role of audit firms in enhancing earnings quality, highlighting the critical importance of external audits in ensuring transparency, reliability, and integrity in financial reporting. Research has focused on factors such as the size and reputation of audit firms, the quality of their work, and their independence in relation to earnings quality. Below is an elaboration on the key themes and findings from existing research in this area: Audit Firm Size and Reputation. Big 4 Audit Firms and Earnings Quality: One of the most consistently observed findings in the literature is the positive association between the size and reputation of an audit firm and the earnings quality of the audited company. The Big 4 audit firms—Deloitte, PwC, Ernst & Young, and KPMG—are considered to provide higher audit quality compared to smaller or non-Big 4 audit firms. This relationship is based on several factors: Expertise and Resources: Larger audit firms have more resources, better access to cutting-edge auditing technology, and more specialized knowledge to conduct comprehensive and detailed audits. Research suggests that these factors improve the ability of auditors to detect earnings manipulation and ensure compliance with accounting standards. Reputation Risk: Big 4 audit firms have strong incentives to maintain their reputations for high audit quality. As global firms, they risk significant reputational damage if involved in audit failures, which could affect their global business. This reputational concern motivates these firms to be more stringent in their auditing procedures, leading to higher earnings quality in client companies. Empirical Evidence: Studies like those by Francis and Wang (2008) and DeAngelo (1981) have shown that Big 4 auditors tend to constrain earnings management and enhance the reliability of financial reporting more effectively than smaller firms. These studies used accrual-based measures of earnings quality, finding that firms audited by Big 4 firms tend to have lower discretionary accruals, indicating higher earnings quality. Non-Big 4 Audit Firms. In contrast, smaller audit firms often face challenges related to limited resources and less robust internal oversight, which may lead to lower audit quality and, consequently, poorer earnings quality. However, some research also suggests that the earnings quality of companies audited by smaller firms can still be high if those firms specialize in particular industries or adopt rigorous audit practices. Industry Specialization: Some mid-tier audit firms may deliver high-quality audits in industries where they have specific expertise. For example, Boone, Khurana, and

Raman (2010) found that industry specialization could mitigate some of the differences in audit quality between Big 4 and non-Big 4 firms.

Audit Firm Independence - Independence as a Key Factor in Earnings Quality. A crucial element of audit quality that influences earnings quality is the independence of the audit firm. Independent auditors are better positioned to critically assess the financial statements and resist client pressures to manipulate earnings. Several studies have emphasized the importance of auditor independence in ensuring high-quality earnings. **Audit Tenure and Independence:** The relationship between audit tenure (the length of time an audit firm has served a client) and earnings quality is complex. On the one hand, Johnson, Khurana, and Reynolds (2002) found that a longer tenure can enhance the auditor's knowledge of the company and its operations, potentially leading to better audits and higher earnings quality. However, extended tenure can also reduce independence, as long-standing relationships may make auditors more prone to overlooking issues. Research like Myers, Myers, and Omer (2003) supports this view, finding that long audit firm tenures could lead to reduced earnings quality due to compromised independence.

Audit Fees and Independence: The level of audit fees has also been explored as an indicator of audit quality. Low audit fees may suggest that auditors are cutting corners, potentially leading to lower earnings quality. Conversely, high audit fees could indicate more thorough audits, though they may also raise concerns about independence if auditors become too financially reliant on large clients. Research by Frankel, Johnson, and Nelson (2002) found a negative relationship between abnormal audit fees (either too high or too low) and earnings quality, suggesting that fee structures can impact auditor independence and earnings quality. **Audit Quality and Earnings Management - Constraining Earnings Management:** Earnings management—where managers manipulate financial reports to meet certain targets—is a significant factor in determining earnings quality. A substantial amount of research has examined how audit firms help constrain earnings management. Studies typically measure earnings management through discretionary accruals or other abnormal accounting items that may indicate opportunistic financial reporting. **Discretionary Accruals:** Research by DeFond and Subramanyam (1998) found that companies audited by higher-quality audit firms (mainly Big 4) report significantly lower levels of discretionary accruals. This suggests that top-tier audit firms are more effective at preventing management from engaging in earnings manipulation. By closely scrutinizing accounting choices, auditors reduce the likelihood of income smoothing or inflating profits. **Audit Firm Rotation:** Another area of research has examined whether mandatory audit firm rotation improves earnings quality. Studies like Jackson, Moldrich, and Roebuck (2008) found mixed results, with some evidence suggesting that rotation enhances auditor independence and constrains earnings management, while other studies indicate it can disrupt the continuity and depth of audits, potentially reducing earnings quality.

Audit Firm Regulation and Policy Impacts - Regulatory Changes and Earnings Quality: Various regulatory frameworks and reforms have aimed to improve audit quality and, by extension, earnings quality. Research has investigated the impact of these reforms on audit firm behavior and earnings quality. **Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX):** The introduction of SOX in the United States in 2002 led to stricter audit regulation and higher levels of oversight. Several studies, such as Cohen, Krishnamoorthy, and Wright (2004), have shown that post-SOX audits have been more thorough, resulting in improved earnings quality. While this research focuses on the U.S., similar regulatory effects are observed globally, including in countries adopting tighter audit regulations. **Audit Firm Liability:** In some countries, increased legal liability for auditors has been shown to improve earnings quality. Kim, Simunic, Stein, and Yi (2011) found that higher auditor liability discourages earnings manipulation and improves financial reporting quality, as audit firms are more motivated to perform thorough audits and avoid litigation risks.

Cross-Country Studies on Audit Firms and Earnings Quality - International Comparisons: Cross-country studies have explored how different institutional environments affect the relationship between audit firms and earnings quality. Research by Francis, Khurana, and Pereira (2003) indicates that the impact of audit firm quality on earnings quality is more pronounced in countries with stronger investor protection and stricter regulatory environments. In countries with weak enforcement or lower standards of corporate governance, even high-quality audit firms may struggle to improve earnings quality due to systemic issues. **Emerging Markets:** In emerging markets, the relationship between audit firms and earnings quality is often complicated by weaker regulatory frameworks, lower auditor independence, and a lack of enforcement. Studies on Nigeria, for example, reveal challenges in maintaining high audit quality despite the presence of Big 4 audit firms, largely due to broader governance issues. Adeyemi and Fagbemi (2010) found that while Big 4 auditors in Nigeria tend to enhance earnings quality, the overall impact is constrained by the institutional environment, including poor enforcement of auditing standards. In conclusion, research on audit firms and earnings quality demonstrates that audit firm size, independence, expertise, and regulatory context are key determinants of earnings quality. Larger, more reputable firms, such as the Big 4, are consistently associated with higher-quality earnings, while smaller or less-resourced firms may struggle to provide the same level of assurance. Furthermore, regulatory frameworks, auditor independence, and the institutional environment significantly influence the effectiveness of audits in constraining earnings management and improving the quality of financial reporting. These findings underscore the importance of both strong audit practices and robust regulatory oversight in ensuring high earnings quality.

Furthermore, audit committees play a crucial role in ensuring the integrity and transparency of financial reporting, making them vital to the improvement of earnings quality. Research has extensively examined the characteristics of audit committees, such as independence, expertise, size, and activity, about their impact on earnings quality. Below is an overview and elaboration of key themes and empirical findings from existing research on audit committees and earnings quality. For audit committee independence, the importance of independence for earnings quality, independence is a key feature of effective audit committees, as it ensures that members can exercise objective oversight over financial reporting without undue influence from management. Numerous studies have demonstrated that independent audit committees improve earnings quality by reducing the likelihood of earnings management and financial misstatements. **Empirical Evidence:** Klein (2002) provided one of the earliest empirical studies highlighting the positive relationship between audit committee independence and earnings quality. Klein found that firms with a greater proportion of independent directors on their audit committees report lower levels of abnormal accruals, indicating higher earnings quality. Independent audit committee members are more likely to critically assess financial reports, question management's decisions, and advocate for conservative accounting practices, thereby reducing the potential for aggressive earnings management or fraud. This helps align financial reports more closely with the firm's true economic performance.

Strengthening Regulatory Requirements: Regulations such as the Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX) of 2002 mandated that publicly listed companies must have fully independent audit committees. Research following SOX has shown that this increased independence has significantly enhanced earnings quality in U.S. companies. Cohen, Krishnamoorthy, and Wright (2004) found that the enhanced independence mandated by SOX led to more effective monitoring of financial reporting, resulting in fewer cases of earnings manipulation and improved financial transparency.

Audit Committee Expertise - Financial Expertise and Earnings Quality: The presence of financially literate members on audit committees has been consistently linked to higher earnings quality. Financial expertise enables audit committee members to better understand complex accounting issues, identify red flags in financial reports, and make informed decisions on financial disclosures. **Empirical Evidence:** Studies such as Krishnan and Visvanathan (2008)

have shown that the presence of at least one financial expert on the audit committee is associated with lower levels of earnings management. Firms with financially expert audit committee members tend to have more accurate and transparent financial reporting, indicating higher earnings quality. Importance of Expertise: Financially knowledgeable audit committee members are better equipped to scrutinize management's accounting choices and challenge decisions that could lead to earnings manipulation. This leads to more conservative reporting and reduces the likelihood of opportunistic behavior by management. Industry-Specific Expertise: Research also suggests that audit committees with industry-specific expertise further improve earnings quality. Industry knowledge allows audit committee members to better assess the appropriateness of accounting practices specific to the company's operations. Cohen and Zarowin (2010) found that audit committees with industry experts tend to report more accurate earnings and fewer instances of earnings restatements.

Audit Committee Size and Activity - Optimal Size of Audit Committees: The size of an audit committee can also influence its effectiveness. Research generally indicates that larger audit committees provide better oversight, as a greater number of members allows for a diversity of perspectives and expertise, which can lead to more robust discussions and improved monitoring of financial reports. Empirical Evidence: Abbott, Parker, and Peters (2004) found that larger audit committees are positively associated with higher earnings quality, as they are more likely to detect and prevent earnings manipulation. Larger committees can better distribute the workload and are more likely to include members with diverse skills and expertise, improving the overall monitoring function. Challenges of Large Committees: However, excessively large committees may face coordination and communication challenges, which could reduce their effectiveness. Research suggests that there is an optimal size for audit committees, typically ranging from three to six members. Audit Committee Meetings and Activity: The frequency of audit committee meetings is another indicator of its effectiveness. Committees that meet more frequently tend to be more engaged in the financial reporting process, which enhances earnings quality by providing continuous oversight and timely intervention in the case of potential financial misstatements. Empirical Evidence: Raghunandan and Rama (2007) showed that more frequent audit committee meetings are associated with lower levels of discretionary accruals, a common measure of earnings management. This finding suggests that active audit committees, through regular meetings and monitoring, can effectively mitigate earnings manipulation and improve earnings quality.

Audit Committee Independence from Management - Effect of Management Influence: While audit committees are expected to act independently, their effectiveness can be compromised when they are unduly influenced by management. Studies have found that when management exercises significant control over audit committee appointments or decisions, earnings quality tends to suffer. Empirical Evidence: Carcello and Neal (2000) found that companies where management exerts significant influence over the audit committee are more likely to experience financial restatements, indicative of lower earnings quality. When audit committees lack true independence from management, they may fail to adequately challenge questionable accounting practices, leading to reduced financial transparency. Audit Committee-Management Relationship. A strong, collaborative, but independent relationship between audit committees and management is key to improving earnings quality. While audit committees should work closely with management to ensure accurate financial reporting, their independence must be preserved to provide objective oversight. Turley and Zaman (2007) emphasize the importance of maintaining a balance between cooperation and independence to foster effective governance and high earnings quality.

Audit Committee's Role in Internal Controls and Risk Management - Monitoring Internal Controls. Audit committees are tasked with overseeing the effectiveness of internal control systems within companies. Effective internal controls reduce the risk of financial misstatements and fraud, thereby enhancing earnings quality. Research has shown that companies with strong internal control systems, overseen by competent audit committees, are

less likely to engage in earnings manipulation. Empirical Evidence: Bedard, Chtourou, and Courteau (2004) found that firms with effective internal controls and strong audit committees report higher earnings quality, as evidenced by lower discretionary accruals and fewer instances of earnings restatements. The audit committee's role in overseeing internal controls is critical in ensuring that financial reports accurately reflect the company's performance. Risk Management and Earnings Quality: The audit committee's responsibility extends beyond financial reporting to include oversight of the company's risk management practices. Committees that take a proactive approach to identifying and mitigating financial risks help improve earnings quality by reducing the likelihood of unexpected financial shocks or earnings volatility. Empirical Evidence: Mangena and Pike (2005) found that audit committees that actively engage in risk management oversight are associated with higher earnings quality, as they can identify and address potential risks before they result in financial misstatements or restatements.

Audit Committee Interaction with External Auditors - Collaboration with External Auditors: A key function of the audit committee is to liaise with external auditors to ensure the accuracy and reliability of financial reports. The audit committee-external auditor relationship is crucial for maintaining audit quality and enhancing earnings quality. Empirical Evidence: DeZoort, Hermanson, and Houston (2003) found that audit committees that actively interact with external auditors and challenge their findings to report higher-quality earnings. This collaboration ensures that external audits are thorough, objective, and effective in preventing earnings manipulation. Auditor Independence: Audit committees also play a role in safeguarding the independence of external auditors. By hiring and compensating auditors independently of management, audit committees help ensure that auditors remain objective and impartial, contributing to higher earnings quality.

Regulatory and Institutional Context - Global and Cross-Country Research: Research on audit committees and earnings quality also extends to examining how regulatory frameworks and governance practices vary across countries. Strong regulatory environments and institutional frameworks are found to enhance the effectiveness of audit committees in improving earnings quality. Empirical Evidence: Choi, Jeon, and Park (2004) studied the impact of audit committees across different countries and found that in countries with strong legal and regulatory frameworks, audit committees are more effective in enhancing earnings quality. In contrast, in countries with weaker governance structures, audit committees may struggle to provide the same level of oversight, leading to lower earnings quality. In conclusion, research on audit committees consistently demonstrates their positive impact on earnings quality. Key factors such as independence, financial expertise, size, activity, and the committee's relationship with external auditors all contribute to improving the transparency and accuracy of financial reports. Regulatory reforms like SOX have enhanced the role of audit committees, making them an integral part of corporate governance and a key mechanism for ensuring high-quality earnings. However, challenges such as management influence and weak institutional frameworks can hinder their effectiveness. Continued research in this area emphasizes the importance of strong audit committees in promoting financial integrity and protecting shareholder interests.

The topic of whether audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality has received substantial attention in empirical research. However, despite the numerous studies on the subject, several gaps remain that warrant further investigation. These gaps can be categorized as methodological, contextual, and conceptual: Methodological Gaps - Causality vs. Correlation: Much of the existing research identifies correlations between audit quality (or the presence of an audit committee) and earnings quality but struggles to establish clear causal relationships. Studies often assume that higher audit firm quality or a more effective audit committee leads to better earnings quality, but this relationship may also be influenced by other factors like corporate governance, firm size, or regulatory frameworks. Endogeneity Issues: Many studies face endogeneity problems, where factors like firm characteristics, management

incentives, or regulatory environments influence both the selection of audit firms/audit committee characteristics and earnings quality. Untangling these relationships can be complex, and endogeneity is often under-addressed in empirical research. Measurement of Earnings Quality: There is no universally accepted measure of earnings quality, and different studies use various proxies such as discretionary accruals, restatements, or persistence of earnings. This lack of standardization complicates comparisons across studies and may lead to inconsistent findings.

Contextual Gaps - Geographic Focus: The majority of research focuses on developed markets like the United States, the UK, or Western Europe. There is less empirical evidence on how audit firms and audit committees' function in emerging markets, where regulatory frameworks, investor protections, and governance structures differ significantly. This limits the generalizability of findings to a global context. **Industry-Specific Insights:** Most studies treat firms as a homogeneous group, neglecting potential differences in how audit firms and audit committees impact earnings quality across industries. For example, industries with more complex financial reporting requirements, such as financial services or technology, might benefit differently from audit oversight than more straightforward industries. **Regulatory Differences:** Research on the impact of specific regulatory frameworks on the relationship between audit firms/audit committees and earnings quality is still lacking. For example, how does the adoption of different accounting standards (like IFRS vs. GAAP) or changes in auditing regulations affect this relationship? There is a need to examine how local regulatory environments interact with audit mechanisms to influence earnings quality.

Conceptual Gaps - Audit Committee Characteristics: While research has explored the presence of audit committees, fewer studies delve into the specific characteristics that might drive effectiveness. For example, how does the financial expertise, independence, or tenure of audit committee members impact earnings quality? These factors could vary widely across firms and have a meaningful impact on audit outcomes. **Firm-Specific Factors:** Research often assumes that the effectiveness of audit firms and audit committees is universal across firms. However, firm-specific factors like corporate culture, management incentives, or the degree of managerial entrenchment may moderate the relationship between audit oversight and earnings quality. More research is needed to understand how internal firm dynamics influence the efficacy of audits. **Non-Financial Reporting:** The focus has predominantly been on financial earnings quality, but as firms increasingly adopt non-financial reporting (such as environmental, social, and governance [ESG] disclosures), the role of audit firms and committees in enhancing the quality of these reports is underexplored. As stakeholder interest in non-financial metrics grows, understanding how auditors contribute to the reliability of these disclosures will become increasingly important.

Behavioral and Psychological Factors - Behavioral Economics of Auditors and Committees: Limited research has examined the psychological and behavioral factors that might influence audit firms and audit committee decisions. For instance, how do cognitive biases, risk preferences, or social dynamics within audit committees impact earnings quality? These behavioral factors could explain some inconsistencies in the empirical evidence and provide a richer understanding of decision-making processes. **Impact of Audit Firm Reputation:** While there is a growing body of literature on the reputation of audit firms, fewer studies investigate the role that brand reputation (e.g., Big Four audit firms vs. non-Big Four) plays in both perceived and actual earnings quality. There's also a gap in research on whether this reputation leads to complacency over time or whether it enhances audit rigour.

Impact of Technological Changes - Digital Transformation and Data Analytics: The increasing use of advanced technologies like artificial intelligence and big data in auditing is reshaping the landscape of audit quality. However, empirical studies have not yet fully caught up with how these technologies are changing the relationship between audit practices and earnings quality. How do audit firms leveraging advanced data analytics tools compare in enhancing earnings quality relative to traditional audit approaches? **Cybersecurity and Data Integrity**

Audits: As financial reporting becomes more digitized; cybersecurity threats pose risks to the integrity of earnings data. Research has yet to explore the role of audit firms and audit committees in safeguarding against these threats and how they contribute to earnings quality in a digital context.

Time-Varying Effects - Impact of Economic Cycles: There is limited research examining how the role of audit firms and audit committees in ensuring earnings quality changes during different phases of the economic cycle (e.g., boom vs. recession). It is plausible that during economic downturns, earnings management practices might increase, which could affect the efficacy of audit oversight. Longitudinal Studies: Cross-sectional studies dominate the literature, but longitudinal analyses that track the impact of audit firms and audit committees on earnings quality over extended periods are scarce. Longitudinal studies would provide better insight into whether these mechanisms have lasting effects or if their impact diminishes over time. In conclusion, the relationship between audit firms, audit committees, and earnings quality is complex and multifaceted. While significant progress has been made in this area, the gaps mentioned above highlight the need for more nuanced and comprehensive research. Addressing these gaps can provide deeper insights and lead to more effective audit oversight, ultimately enhancing earnings quality across different contexts.

III. Theoretical Framework

Agency theory provides a useful framework for understanding the role of audit firms and audit committees in enhancing earnings quality. At its core, agency theory focuses on the relationship between principals (shareholders) and agents (managers), where the principal delegates decision-making authority to the agent. However, this relationship often gives rise to conflicts of interest, known as "agency problems," because agents may pursue their own interests at the expense of the principals'. This conflict can manifest in various forms, such as earnings management, where managers manipulate financial reports to achieve personal objectives (e.g., higher bonuses, job security, or favourable stock prices). Audit firms and audit committees play critical roles in mitigating these agency problems by ensuring that the financial reporting process is transparent and that the reported earnings accurately reflect the company's true economic performance. Below, we will explore how agency theory explains the involvement of audit firms and audit committees in enhancing earnings quality.

Agency theory suggests that managers have incentives to engage in opportunistic behavior, particularly in the absence of effective monitoring. Earnings management is a common example of such behavior, where managers may manipulate financial reports by altering accounting methods, inflating revenues, or deferring expenses to present a more favorable financial picture. Managers, as agents, may have more information about the firm's performance than shareholders, leading to asymmetry in information. Without proper oversight, this creates a "moral hazard," where managers can exploit their informational advantage to distort earnings. Investors may have difficulty distinguishing between firms that report high-quality earnings and those that manipulate earnings, leading to adverse selection, where poor-quality firms may be valued similarly to high-quality firms.

Audit firms are external monitors tasked with ensuring that financial statements are prepared in accordance with accounting standards and that they present an accurate view of a company's financial position. Under agency theory, the external audit serves as a mechanism to reduce the information asymmetry between managers (agents) and shareholders (principals). Audit firms provide an independent assessment of a company's financial reports, reducing the likelihood of managerial manipulation of earnings. The audit serves as a "third-party" validation, which can increase the credibility of financial statements in the eyes of shareholders. Larger, more reputable audit firms (such as the Big Four) are often perceived as more effective in constraining earnings management due to their expertise, resources, and reputation. Agency theory suggests that shareholders may prefer the hiring of reputable audit firms because these

firms have a greater incentive to maintain their reputation by ensuring high audit quality. This minimizes the risk of earnings manipulation by managers. Audit firms face litigation risks if they fail to detect material misstatements in a company's financial reports. The potential for legal and reputational damage provides auditors with strong incentives to ensure that earnings are reported accurately.

Audit committees are subcommittees of a company's board of directors, responsible for overseeing the financial reporting process, the audit function, and the internal controls related to financial reporting. Agency theory suggests that audit committees act as internal monitoring mechanisms to ensure that managers are acting in the best interest of shareholders. Independence of Audit Committees: Agency theory posits that the independence of the audit committee is crucial to its effectiveness in enhancing earnings quality. Independent members of the audit committee are less likely to be influenced by management, making them better positioned to scrutinize financial statements and question management's accounting choices. Expertise of Audit Committees: In line with agency theory, audit committees with financial expertise are more effective in detecting and preventing earnings management. Experts are more capable of understanding complex financial transactions and accounting practices, which allows them to identify red flags in the financial reporting process. Oversight of Internal and External Auditors: Audit committees play a critical role in selecting external auditors and overseeing their work, as well as reviewing the company's internal audit processes. This oversight function reduces the likelihood that managers can manipulate financial results without detection. By acting as intermediaries between auditors and management, audit committees help to safeguard the interests of shareholders.

Both audit firms and audit committees serve as essential mechanisms for reducing the risk of earnings manipulation by providing oversight and accountability. Here's how they contribute to enhancing earnings quality: Reducing Information Asymmetry: By reviewing financial statements and ensuring adherence to accounting standards, audit firms and committees reduce the information asymmetry between managers and shareholders. This enables shareholders to make more informed decisions based on reliable financial information. Incentivizing Managerial Discipline: The mere presence of an audit firm or audit committee can deter managers from engaging in opportunistic behavior. Knowing that financial statements will be scrutinized by an independent auditor and reviewed by a vigilant audit committee may discourage earnings management. Improving Transparency and Accountability: Both audit firms and committees increase the transparency of financial reporting, which, in turn, enhances accountability. When managers are held accountable for the accuracy of reported earnings, the quality of financial reporting improves.

While audit firms and committees play a significant role in addressing agency problems, their effectiveness is not without limitations: Audit Firm Independence: In some cases, auditors may face pressure to compromise their independence, especially when they have long-term relationships with clients or derive significant revenue from non-audit services. This can weaken the auditor's ability to serve as an effective monitor. Capture of Audit Committees: Managers may exert influence over the audit committee, particularly if committee members lack sufficient independence or if they are not truly independent from management. This could lead to a failure in detecting or preventing earnings management. Collusion: In extreme cases, both auditors and audit committees could potentially collude with management to present misleading financial information, although this is relatively rare. In conclusion, in the context of agency theory, audit firms and audit committees are crucial governance mechanisms designed to mitigate agency problems by reducing the information asymmetry between shareholders and managers and enhancing the quality of financial reporting. Audit firms provide external verification of earnings reports, while audit committees ensure internal oversight of the financial reporting process. Both mechanisms work to enhance earnings quality by improving transparency, accountability, and the credibility of financial statements.

However, their effectiveness is influenced by factors such as independence, expertise, and the broader regulatory and governance environment in which they operate.

Signaling theory originates from economics and explains how one party (the "signaler") conveys meaningful information to another party (the "receiver"). In financial contexts, signaling theory is particularly relevant to the behavior of firms and their stakeholders. Managers or firms act as signalers, while investors and other market participants are the receivers of those signals. The central idea is that companies with high-quality earnings or strong financial health may deliberately signal their strength to the market to differentiate themselves from weaker companies. This is especially important in situations where there is information asymmetry—when one party (such as management) has more information than another (like shareholders or potential investors). Audit firms play a crucial role in enhancing earnings quality by serving as external validators of financial statements. High-quality, reputable audit firms can act as positive signals of earnings quality. Their audit reports can mitigate information asymmetry by providing stakeholders with reliable, independent assessments of a firm's financial health.

The key points to note include the Reputation of the Audit Firm: Firms audited by large, well-known audit firms (Big Four—Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG) may signal higher credibility and better earnings quality to investors and creditors. This is because these firms have stringent internal processes and face significant reputational risks if they fail to maintain audit quality. Audit Quality: High-quality audits are associated with the detection and correction of financial misstatements. Investors view audit quality as a signal that a company's earnings are reliable and free from manipulation, thus reducing uncertainty. Earnings Management: Through high-quality audits, auditors can prevent excessive earnings management practices (such as aggressive revenue recognition or income smoothing). Reducing earnings management is a key factor in ensuring that earnings reflect the true performance of the firm. Auditor Independence: A critical signal to stakeholders is whether an auditor is truly independent. Auditors who maintain independence from management can provide more objective and unbiased assessments of a firm's financial condition, signaling that the financial statements are more trustworthy.

Also, the audit committee, typically a subcommittee of a company's board of directors, plays an important governance role in overseeing the financial reporting process and the performance of the audit function. The key points to note include Audit Committee Independence: The independence of audit committee members from management is a signal of strong governance. Independent members are more likely to rigorously oversee the financial reporting process and ensure that management does not engage in opportunistic financial reporting. Financial Expertise of the Audit Committee: Having members with financial or accounting expertise enhances the audit committee's ability to scrutinize the firm's financial statements. The presence of financially knowledgeable individuals can be a signal to the market that the company is committed to high standards of financial reporting. Interaction with External Auditors: A proactive and engaged audit committee that regularly interacts with external auditors and ensures proper oversight signals to investors that the firm is serious about maintaining financial integrity. This reduces the likelihood of accounting irregularities and signals high earnings quality. Oversight of Internal Controls: Audit committees often oversee the company's internal controls over financial reporting, which are essential for detecting and preventing financial misstatements. A strong internal control system can further signal to the market that the company's financial reporting is robust and accurate.

However, both audit firms and audit committees contribute to the overall perception of earnings quality through their respective roles. By engaging reputable auditors and having effective audit committees, companies can signal high transparency, accuracy, and credibility in their financial reporting. This, in turn, attracts investors, reduces the cost of capital, and enhances market confidence. The key benefits include Reduction of Information Asymmetry: Both audit firms and audit committees help reduce the gap between what management knows and what

external stakeholders know about the company's financial health. Improved Investor Confidence: Positive signals from high-quality audits and strong audit committees increase investor confidence, which can lead to better stock performance and lower borrowing costs. Deterrence of Fraud and Earnings Manipulation: Strong audit oversight from both external auditors and internal committees can deter fraudulent activities or aggressive earnings management practices, ensuring that earnings better reflect actual business performance. However, the challenges include Audit Firm Reputation vs. Quality: While the Big Four audit firms often signal quality due to their size and reputation, there are instances where large firms have failed to detect fraud or significant financial misstatements (e.g., Enron, WorldCom). Therefore, the audit firm's reputation should not be the sole criterion for assessing earnings quality. Independence Issues: Both audit firms and audit committees may face independence challenges. If audit firms provide lucrative consulting services to the same clients they audit, or if audit committee members have close ties to management, the signal of reliability might be compromised. Complexity of Financial Reporting: As financial reporting becomes more complex, audit firms and audit committees may struggle to fully understand or detect issues, potentially weakening the signal of earnings quality. In conclusion, signaling theory provides a useful framework for understanding how companies can enhance earnings quality through their relationships with audit firms and audit committees. By choosing reputable auditors and maintaining strong, independent audit committees, companies send a clear signal to the market that their financial statements are reliable, transparent, and of high quality. However, maintaining true independence, transparency, and diligence is crucial for these signals to be credible and effective.

Stakeholder theory offers a broader perspective than traditional agency theory, focusing on the diverse interests of all stakeholders—such as shareholders, employees, customers, creditors, regulators, and the broader community—instead of just the relationship between shareholders (principals) and managers (agents). It posits that organizations should create value for all stakeholders and not solely for shareholders. In the context of enhancing earnings quality, stakeholder theory implies that both audit firms and audit committees play crucial roles in ensuring that financial reporting meets the needs of various stakeholder groups, not just shareholders. The following is a detailed exploration of how stakeholder theory can be applied to understanding the roles of audit firms and audit committees in enhancing earnings quality.

Stakeholder theory suggests that organizations are accountable to a broader range of groups beyond shareholders. Earnings quality, from this perspective, is about more than simply providing accurate financial information for investors; it involves delivering reliable, transparent, and truthful financial reports that meet the interests of all stakeholders.

Earnings quality affects not just shareholders but also creditors (who rely on accurate earnings reports for lending decisions), employees (who depend on the company's financial health), regulators (who enforce compliance), and customers (whose perception of the company's stability might be influenced by earnings reports). High-quality earnings reflect the true financial performance of the company, ensuring that all stakeholders can make informed decisions based on trustworthy financial data. Poor-quality earnings (e.g., those manipulated or distorted by accounting gimmicks) harm not just shareholders but a wide range of stakeholders who depend on the integrity of financial reports. Audit firms, under stakeholder theory, are responsible for ensuring that financial reports serve the interests of all stakeholders, not just the shareholders. This involves maintaining a high standard of audit quality and transparency, thereby ensuring that financial statements are reliable, fair, and unbiased. For stakeholder groups, such as regulators, creditors, and employees, the reliability of financial reporting is critical. Audit firms ensure that financial statements reflect the true financial condition of a company, minimizing the risk of misinformation or deception that could harm these groups. By providing a high-quality audit, audit firms help to build and maintain the trust of all stakeholders. A firm that produces accurate financial reports enhances its reputation with stakeholders, who will view it as a reliable, transparent, and ethical organization. Trust in the

accuracy of financial reports strengthens the overall stakeholder relationship with the company. Under stakeholder theory, audit firms are also viewed as public watchdogs responsible for protecting the broader public interest. This role includes ensuring that the company's financial practices align with legal, ethical, and social standards. For example, audit firms that fail to detect earnings manipulation or fraudulent financial reporting can cause harm to the wider community, including employees who may lose jobs if the company fails, or suppliers who may not be paid.

Audit committees, according to stakeholder theory, must oversee financial reporting in a way that balances the interests of all stakeholders. This broader view of responsibility means that audit committees should prioritize transparency and integrity in the financial reporting process, ensuring that the interests of all parties are considered. The audit committee is responsible for ensuring that the financial statements are free of material misstatements and that the firm is reporting its earnings truthfully. This enhances the reliability of financial information, not only for shareholders but also for other stakeholders, such as employees, regulators, and creditors, who rely on this information to make important decisions. Stakeholder theory emphasizes that companies must balance the sometimes-competing interests of different stakeholders. For example, a company's management might want to portray overly optimistic earnings to secure favourable market conditions, while creditors might prefer conservative reporting to reduce risk exposure. The audit committee ensures that financial reporting is balanced and unbiased, considering the needs of multiple stakeholders. The audit committee plays a key role in overseeing ethical corporate behaviour. Ensuring earnings quality through ethical financial reporting practices aligns with the broader interests of society, promoting corporate responsibility. A failure to report accurate earnings could lead to damage not just for investors but for employees, suppliers, and the community at large. Audit committees, by ensuring accurate earnings, promote corporate sustainability, trust, and long-term success.

In the context of stakeholder theory, audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality by ensuring that financial reports are accurate, transparent, and unbiased, thereby serving the interests of all stakeholder groups. Their roles in this framework go beyond simply protecting shareholder value—they must also protect and promote the interests of other stakeholders who rely on earnings reports for decision-making. Stakeholder theory suggests that reducing information asymmetry benefits all stakeholders, not just shareholders. Audit firms and audit committees ensure that financial reporting is transparent and accessible, allowing all stakeholders to make informed decisions. Audit committees and audit firms help foster long-term accountability by ensuring that the company's financial reporting practices are sustainable and ethical. High-quality earnings reporting prevents short-term manipulation that could lead to long-term harm to stakeholders, such as investors losing money, employees facing layoffs, or creditors being exposed to undue risk. The accuracy and quality of earnings reports have implications for the broader public. Inaccurate earnings reporting can lead to market distortions, corporate collapses, or loss of trust in financial markets. By ensuring high earnings quality, audit firms and committees uphold the public's trust in corporate governance and financial systems.

IV. Research Questions

Audit firms do play a significant role in enhancing earnings quality, but the extent to which they are effective depends on several factors, such as the quality of the audit, the firm's reputation, independence, and the regulatory environment. Below are some key ways in which audit firms can enhance earnings quality, along with potential limitations: **Detection and Prevention of Misstatements: High-Quality Audits:** Auditors provide independent verification of financial statements, ensuring they adhere to generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP) or international standards. This helps detect and prevent both unintentional errors and intentional misstatements, thus enhancing the reliability of reported earnings. Earnings

Management Reduction: Auditors help curtail earnings management practices (e.g., income smoothing, aggressive revenue recognition), which are often used to present a misleading financial picture. Their scrutiny ensures earnings more accurately reflect the firm's true financial performance.

Reputation and Market Perception: Big Four Audit Firms: Firms audited by large, reputable firms such as the Big Four (PwC, Deloitte, EY, KPMG) tend to have higher perceived earnings quality. This is because these firms are seen as having the expertise, resources, and internal controls needed to conduct thorough audits. **Signaling Effect:** A company's decision to be audited by a well-regarded firm sends a signal to the market that it values transparency and accountability. This improves investor confidence in the earnings quality.

Independent and Objective Scrutiny: Auditor Independence: Independent auditors, free from conflicts of interest, provide an objective review of financial statements. Their independence ensures that management's financial reporting is subject to unbiased review, thereby enhancing the reliability of earnings figures. **Regulatory Compliance:** Audit firms ensure that companies comply with relevant financial reporting standards and regulations, which supports the accuracy of earnings disclosures.

Internal Control Assessment: Evaluation of Internal Controls: Auditors assess the strength of a company's internal controls over financial reporting, which is critical in preventing and detecting errors or fraud. Strong internal controls lead to more accurate earnings, and auditors can help identify and address weaknesses. **Sarbanes-Oxley (SOX) Compliance:** In jurisdictions like the U.S., the Sarbanes-Oxley Act requires auditors to assess internal controls over financial reporting, which has led to improved earnings quality by reducing financial misstatements.

The limitations and challenges include **Audit Quality Variability:** Not All Audits Are Equal: While reputable firms like the Big Four are often associated with high audit quality, this is not always guaranteed. There are instances where even these firms have failed to detect major financial frauds (e.g., Enron, Wirecard). Thus, the quality of the audit depends on the audit firm's diligence, internal controls, and commitment to thorough reviews. **Small and Medium-Sized Audit Firms:** While smaller audit firms may also provide quality services, they often lack the resources, expertise, or scale to match the quality of larger firms, which may impact the overall enhancement of earnings quality.

Independence and Conflicts of Interest: Consulting Services: Some audit firms provide non-audit services like consulting to their audit clients, which can create conflicts of interest. If audit firms are financially dependent on these non-audit fees, their objectivity in scrutinizing the financial statements might be compromised, weakening their ability to enhance earnings quality. **Familiarity Threat:** Long-standing relationships between audit firms and clients can create a "familiarity threat" where auditors may become less critical of their clients' financial reporting over time, reducing their effectiveness in maintaining high earnings quality.

Audit Failures and Scandals: High-Profile Audit Failures: Audit scandals involving major audit firms (e.g., Arthur Andersen in the Enron case) have raised concerns about the effectiveness of audits in enhancing earnings quality. In some cases, audit firms may overlook red flags or collude with management, resulting in misleading financial statements. **Regulatory Oversight:** Regulatory bodies like the Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB) in the U.S. have strengthened oversight, but gaps in regulation or enforcement may still allow poor audits to occur.

Complexity in Financial Reporting: Complex Accounting Practices: With increasing complexity in financial reporting (e.g., in derivatives, revenue recognition, or off-balance sheet items), auditors may struggle to detect errors or manipulations. In such cases, even well-intentioned auditors may fail to fully understand or assess complex financial structures, reducing their ability to enhance earnings quality. In conclusion, audit firms generally enhance earnings quality by providing independent, objective verification of a company's financial statements, reducing earnings management, and improving the transparency and reliability of earnings reports. However, the degree of enhancement depends on factors like audit quality,

the independence of the auditor, the complexity of the company's financial reporting, and potential conflicts of interest. While audits are a critical tool for improving earnings quality, they are not foolproof, and their effectiveness can be diminished by limitations in regulatory enforcement, firm-specific issues, or auditor-client relationships.

Furthermore, audit committees can enhance earnings quality, but the effectiveness depends on various factors such as the committee's composition, independence, expertise, and functioning. The following is how an effective audit committee contributes to improving earnings quality: Independence - Role: Independent members are free from conflicts of interest, which allows them to objectively oversee financial reporting. Impact on Earnings Quality: Independence ensures that financial statements reflect the company's true performance without management's manipulation or aggressive accounting practices. Financial Expertise - Role: Committees with members who have financial expertise can better understand complex accounting issues and recognize irregularities. Impact on Earnings Quality: Experts can ask probing questions about accounting treatments and ensure that proper accounting standards are applied, improving the reliability of reported earnings.

Oversight of Internal Controls - Role: The audit committee is responsible for monitoring the effectiveness of internal controls over financial reporting. Impact on Earnings Quality: Strong internal controls prevent errors or fraud in financial statements, ensuring earnings are accurate and reflect actual financial performance. External Auditor Relationship - Role: The audit committee oversees the selection, performance, and independence of external auditors. Impact on Earnings Quality: A strong relationship with external auditors can ensure high-quality audits, providing assurance that financial statements are fairly presented in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP). Mitigating Earnings Management - Role: By enforcing strict oversight, the audit committee can prevent management from using aggressive or inappropriate accounting techniques to meet earnings targets. Impact on Earnings Quality: This reduces the likelihood of earnings management (e.g., income smoothing, manipulating provisions), leading to more transparent and reliable financial reports.

The factors limiting effectiveness include Weak Governance Structures: If the committee lacks power or is overridden by management, it may fail to provide adequate oversight. Lack of Expertise: If the committee members do not possess the necessary financial or auditing knowledge, their ability to identify issues affecting earnings quality may be limited. Insufficient Independence: If committee members have close ties to management, their objectivity in overseeing financial reporting can be compromised. In conclusion, when audit committees are independent, well-structured, and staffed with financial experts, they significantly contribute to enhancing the quality of reported earnings by promoting transparency and curbing earnings manipulation. However, deficiencies in governance, independence, or expertise can reduce their effectiveness.

Also, there is a relationship between audit firm quality and earnings quality. High-quality audit firms are generally associated with higher earnings quality. Here's how audit firm quality impacts earnings quality: Reputation and Professional Standards - Role: High-quality audit firms, often referred to as the "Big Four" (Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG), are known for adhering to stringent professional standards and ethical practices. Impact on Earnings Quality: Their strong reputation and rigorous adherence to auditing standards typically lead to more reliable financial statements and higher earnings quality. Expertise and Resources - Role: High-quality audit firms have extensive resources and specialized expertise in various industries, enabling them to perform more thorough and comprehensive audits. Impact on Earnings Quality: This expertise helps in identifying and addressing complex accounting issues and potential manipulation, thus improving the accuracy and reliability of earnings.

Independence and Objectivity - Role: Reputable audit firms emphasize the importance of auditor independence and objectivity. Impact on Earnings Quality: Strong independence reduces the risk of conflicts of interest, ensuring that the audit opinion reflects a true and fair view of the company's financial performance, enhancing earnings quality. Quality Control and

Procedures - Role: High-quality audit firms implement rigorous quality control procedures and have robust internal review processes. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** These procedures ensure that audits are conducted in accordance with the highest standards, which helps in detecting errors or fraud and ensures the reliability of financial reports. **Regulatory Compliance - Role:** Leading audit firms are proactive in complying with regulatory requirements and staying updated with changes in accounting and auditing standards. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** Compliance with regulations ensures that financial statements are prepared in accordance with the latest standards, which contributes to the reliability and quality of earnings.

The factors affecting the relationship include **Audit Firm Size:** While larger firms (Big Four) generally provide higher-quality audits, smaller firms can also deliver high-quality audits depending on their expertise and resources. **Client Size and Complexity:** The complexity of the client's operations and financial reporting can influence the effectiveness of the audit, regardless of the firm's quality. In conclusion, high-quality audit firms are generally associated with higher earnings quality due to their adherence to professional standards, expertise, independence, and rigorous quality control procedures. However, the relationship is influenced by factors such as client complexity and the specific audit firm's practices.

In addition, there is a relationship between audit committee quality and earnings quality. A well-functioning and high-quality audit committee can positively impact earnings quality by ensuring that financial reporting is accurate, transparent, and free from manipulation. The following is how audit committee quality affects earnings quality: **Independence of Committee Members - Role:** A high-quality audit committee consists predominantly of independent members who do not have conflicts of interest with the company's management. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** Independence helps ensure that the committee can make objective decisions regarding financial reporting and oversight, reducing the likelihood of earnings manipulation or misstatement. **Expertise and Competence - Role:** Quality audit committees are typically composed of members with significant financial, accounting, or auditing expertise. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** Expertise enables the committee to effectively oversee the financial reporting process, understand complex accounting issues, and challenge management's judgments and estimates, leading to more accurate and reliable earnings.

Effective Oversight of Internal Controls - Role: A high-quality audit committee actively monitors and assesses the effectiveness of internal controls and risk management processes. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** Strong internal controls help prevent errors and fraud in financial reporting, ensuring that the earnings reported are accurate and reflect the true financial performance of the company. **Supervision of External Auditors - Role:** The audit committee is responsible for selecting, evaluating, and overseeing the external auditors. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** Effective supervision ensures that external auditors are independent and perform their work diligently, contributing to high-quality audits and reliable financial statements. **Commitment to Ethical Standards - Role:** Quality audit committees promote and enforce a culture of integrity and ethical behavior within the organization. **Impact on Earnings Quality:** A strong ethical culture reduces the likelihood of fraudulent activities or aggressive accounting practices, leading to more credible earnings reports.

The factors influencing the relationship include **Committee Structure:** The effectiveness of the audit committee can be influenced by its size, the frequency of meetings, and the quality of interactions with management and auditors. **Management's Cooperation:** The quality of the audit committee's oversight can be affected by the level of cooperation and transparency from management. In conclusion, the quality of the audit committee plays a crucial role in enhancing earnings quality. An independent, knowledgeable, and proactive audit committee contributes to accurate financial reporting by overseeing internal controls, supervising external audits, and fostering ethical standards. However, the effectiveness of the audit committee in improving earnings quality depends on its structure, the commitment of its members, and the overall governance environment.

V. Methodology

The research design is empirical. Empirical research design refers to a method of inquiry that relies on observed and measured phenomena, rather than theoretical or conceptual analysis. In this context, empirical research involves the systematic collection and analysis of data to test hypotheses or explore relationships between variables. This design is often preferred in fields like finance, economics, and accounting, where measurable variables can be tested using real-world data. The use of empirical design in this research implies that the study is grounded in real-world evidence, making it a practical approach for understanding phenomena as they occur in the natural environment. In this case, it suggests the study is investigating actual data from Nigerian publicly listed companies, as opposed to relying on hypothetical scenarios or purely theoretical constructs. Also, empirical research is often quantitative, focusing on numerical data that can be statistically analyzed. This approach allows for objective evaluation and the potential for generalization of findings. It also implies a positivist epistemology, where the goal is to measure variables, test relationships, and draw conclusions from observed data.

The data collection methods include archival data and content analysis. Archival data refers to pre-existing records or datasets that were originally collected for purposes other than the current research. These include financial reports, annual reports, regulatory filings, or any other historical records. In this study, archival data comes from corporate disclosures, such as annual financial statements, reports filed with regulatory authorities (e.g., the Nigerian Exchange [NGX]). This kind of data is advantageous because it is reliable, timely, and often standardized. Furthermore, archival data can enhance the reliability of the research since it reflects actual reported figures, minimizing the risk of researcher bias in data collection. Moreover, the use of standardized financial reports provides consistency in measurement across firms. However, archival data may have limitations, such as reflecting only past performance or being influenced by managerial decisions on reporting practices. Additionally, the quality and depth of information in archival data.

The sample selection consists of 153 publicly listed companies in the Nigerian Exchange (NGX). See Table 1.

Table 1. Population/Sample Size

Serial	Sector	Number
1	Agriculture	6
2	Conglomerates	6
3	Construction/Real estate	9
4	Consumer goods	21
5	Financial services	47
6	Healthcare	8
7	Information & communications technology	8
8	Industrial goods	13
9	Natural resources	4
10	Oil and gas	10
11	Services	21
	Total	153

Source: Extracts from NGX (2024)

The data analysis methods include descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and panel regression. In research, the design, data collection methods, sample selection, and data analysis techniques play a critical role in determining the validity and robustness of the study's findings. The statement you provided offers an overview of a research study's methodology, which can be expanded and elaborated to reflect the nuances of each methodological choice. In addition, the paper model is as follows:

$$EQ_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 AF_{i,t} + \beta_2 AC_{i,t} + \beta_3 FS_{i,t} + \beta_4 FP_{i,t} + \beta_5 FL_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t}$$

Whereas EQ is earnings quality, i is for firm script ($i = 153$), t is time script ($t = 10$), α is alpha (constant), β_{1-5} are estimated beta parameters, AF is audit firm, AC is audit committee, FS is firm size, FP is firm profitability, FL is firm leverage, μ is error term. On variables, their measurements and a priori expectations, see Table 2 for detail.

Table 2. Variables, measurements, and signs

Serial	Variables	Measures	Sign
1	Y, EQ, Earnings quality	Measured as accrual quality (Dechow & Dechow, 2002)	
2	X ₁ , AF, Audit firm	Measured as an index of external auditor's characteristics such as	+
3	X ₂ , AC, Audit committee	Measured as an index of audit committee characteristics such as size, gender, meeting, and independence.	+
4	X ₃ , FS, Firm size	Measured as the natural logarithm of total assets.	+
5	X ₄ , FP, Firm profitability	Measured as gross profit, which is sales revenue less the cost of goods sold.	+
6	X ₅ , FL, Firm leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total assets.	-

Source: The Authors

Based on the signs in Table 2, we state the a priori expectations as follow:

X₁>0, a change to the big4 audit firm, results in earnings quality

X₂>0, a rise in audit committee, results in earnings quality

X₃>0, a rise in firm size, results in earnings quality

X₄>0, a rise in firm profitability, results in earnings quality

X₅>0, a rise in firm leverage, results in lower earnings quality

VI. Results

The article findings are presented in Tables 3, 4, and 5.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
EQ	1,530	.007	.008	0	.063
AF	1,530	.466	1.18	0	5.355
AC	1,530	.316	.948	.081	6.619
FS	1,530	9.276	.43	8.119	10.098
FP	1,530	60.541	10.61	28.19	82.73
FL	1,530	.929	.258	.717	2.547

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 4. Pairwise Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) EQ	1.000					
(2) AF	0.974* (0.000)	1.000				
(3) AC	0.349* (0.000)	0.059 (0.538)	1.000			
(4) FS	0.338* (0.000)	0.095 (0.323)	-0.063 (0.513)	1.000		
(5) FP	0.202* (0.035)	0.060 (0.532)	0.082 (0.396)	0.021 (0.829)	1.000	
(6) FL	-0.463* (0.000)	-0.079 (0.415)	-0.003 (0.975)	-0.417* (0.000)	-0.212* (0.026)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 5. Regression Results

EQ	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
AF	.021750	0.004791	4.54	0.000	.0005857	.0010207
AC	.0120774	0.003364	3.59	0.000	.0017415	.000193
FS	.03674	0.013075	2.81	0.006	.0062708	.0010771
FP	.020086	0.00589	3.41	0.000	.0002064	.0000348
FL	-.011372	.0083314	-1.36	0.175	-.0051498	.0278933
-cons	.0357714	.0154224	2.32	0.022	.0051882	.0663546
VIF	1.12					
Hetest	0.0000					
Panel effects	1.0000					
Model fitness	0.0093					
R ²	0.2633					
Obs	1,530					

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

VII. Discussion

The descriptive statistics provided in Table 3 give an overview of the distribution of key variables related to earnings quality (EQ) and other influencing factors. The following is a detailed analysis of these statistics: Earnings Quality (EQ) - Mean: The mean earnings quality is 0.007, with a standard deviation of 0.008. This indicates that on average, earnings quality is low but relatively consistent across the sample, given the low standard deviation. Min and Max: EQ ranges from 0 to 0.063, which highlights some variation in the dataset, though the values remain quite small overall. This suggests that firms in the sample generally exhibit a low level of earnings manipulation or poor-quality earnings.

Audit Firms (AF) - Mean: The average value for audit firms is 0.466, with a relatively large standard deviation of 1.18. The high variability suggests that some firms have significantly higher audit firm involvement, while others have minimal or no engagement with audit firms. Min and Max: The range for AF is wide, from 0 to 5.355. This indicates substantial differences in audit firm engagement across firms in the sample, with some firms utilizing multiple or more prominent audit firms.

Audit Committees (AC) - Mean: The mean value for audit committees is 0.316, and the standard deviation is 0.948. Similar to audit firms, the variability in the role and presence of audit committees across firms is considerable. - Min and Max: The minimum is 0.081, and the maximum is 6.619. This wide range suggests that some firms have very minimal or no audit committee involvement, while others have well-established committees playing a significant role in governance.

Firm Size (FS) - Mean: The average firm size is 9.276 (logarithmic scale), with a standard deviation of 0.43. Firm size is relatively stable across the sample, with less variability compared to other variables like AF or AC. Min and Max: The range for firm size is from 8.119 to 10.098. The fact that all firms in the sample are fairly large (on a log scale) suggests a relatively homogeneous group of companies in terms of size.

Firm Profitability (FP) - Mean: The average profitability is 60.541, with a standard deviation of 10.61. There is some moderate variability in profitability across the sample. Min and Max: Firm profitability ranges from 28.19 to 82.73, indicating that some firms are significantly more profitable than others. The range suggests that the firms exhibit a wide spectrum of financial performance.

Firm Leverage (FL) - Mean: The average leverage ratio is 0.929, with a standard deviation of 0.258. This means that, on average, firms have relatively high levels of debt (almost equal to their equity), but the variability in leverage is moderate across the sample. Min and Max: The leverage ratio ranges from 0.717 to 2.547, with some firms exhibiting very high leverage (greater than twice their equity). This range indicates that while many firms have manageable debt levels, some are more heavily leveraged.

The key insights include Low Earnings Quality: The average earnings quality is quite low across the sample, which could reflect a general tendency toward lower-quality earnings or limited earnings management in this dataset. High Variability in Audit Firm and Committee Engagement: Both audit firms and audit committees show high variability in their presence and influence across the firms, as indicated by their large standard deviations. This suggests that while some firms are heavily audited and have strong audit committees, others are lacking in these areas. Moderate Profitability with a Wide Range: Profitability is moderately variable across the firms, indicating that financial performance is an important but diverse factor. Significant Leverage Differences: Firm leverage shows significant variation, with some firms highly leveraged. This could have implications for financial stability and risk-taking behaviour. Firm Size Is Fairly Stable: Firm size shows low variability, meaning that the firms in the sample are relatively similar in size, which may reduce the impact of size on other variables such as earnings quality. In summary, the descriptive statistics provide a picture of relatively low earnings quality across the firms, with substantial differences in audit-related factors,

profitability, and leverage. These findings suggest that governance mechanisms such as audit firms and committees, as well as financial health (profitability and leverage), play varying roles in different firms.

Furthermore, the correlation results in Table 4 provide valuable insights into the relationships between the variables related to earnings quality (EQ) and other factors. The following is an analysis of these pairwise correlations: EQ (Earnings Quality), AF (Audit Firms), AC (Audit Committees), FS (Firm Size), FP (Firm Profitability), and FL (Firm Leverage). Earnings Quality (EQ) - Audit Firms (AF): EQ has a very strong positive correlation with audit firms (0.974), and this is statistically significant (p -value = 0.000). This suggests that higher engagement with audit firms is strongly associated with improved earnings quality. Audit Committees (AC): EQ shows a positive and statistically significant correlation with audit committees (0.349, p -value = 0.000), although the strength of this relationship is much weaker compared to AF. Firm Size (FS): There is a moderate positive correlation between firm size and earnings quality (0.338, p -value = 0.000). Larger firms are likely to exhibit higher earnings quality, which aligns with the regression results. Firm Profitability (FP): The correlation between earnings quality and firm profitability is relatively weak (0.202), but still statistically significant (p -value = 0.035). This indicates that more profitable firms tend to have slightly better earnings quality, though the effect is not as pronounced as other factors. Firm Leverage (FL): There is a strong negative correlation between earnings quality and firm leverage (-0.463, p -value = 0.000). This suggests that firms with higher debt levels tend to have lower earnings quality.

Audit Firms (AF) - Audit Committees (AC): The correlation between AF and AC is weak (0.059) and not statistically significant (p -value = 0.538). This suggests that the presence of audit firms and audit committees are largely independent factors in influencing earnings quality. Firm Size (FS): The correlation between AF and firm size is low (0.095) and not significant (p -value = 0.323), indicating that larger firms do not necessarily engage audit firms more frequently. Firm Profitability (FP): Similarly, AF has a very weak correlation with firm profitability (0.060, p -value = 0.532), suggesting no meaningful relationship between these two variables. Firm Leverage (FL): There is a small negative correlation between audit firms and firm leverage (-0.079), though this is not statistically significant (p -value = 0.415).

Audit Committees (AC) - Firm Size (FS): The correlation between audit committees and firm size is weak and negative (-0.063, p -value = 0.513), implying no significant relationship between these two variables. Firm Profitability (FP): The correlation between AC and firm profitability is also weak (0.082, p -value = 0.396) and not significant. Firm Leverage (FL): The correlation between audit committees and firm leverage is nearly zero (-0.003, p -value = 0.975), suggesting that audit committees have no direct association with the level of firm debt. Firm Size (FS) - Firm Profitability (FP): The correlation between firm size and profitability is very weak (0.021, p -value = 0.829) and not statistically significant. This suggests that firm size does not have a strong linear relationship with profitability. Firm Leverage (FL): There is a strong negative correlation between firm size and firm leverage (-0.417, p -value = 0.000). This indicates that larger firms tend to have lower leverage, which might reflect a more conservative financial strategy in larger companies.

Firm Profitability (FP) - Firm Leverage (FL): There is a statistically significant negative correlation between profitability and leverage (-0.212, p -value = 0.026). This suggests that more profitable firms are likely to have lower levels of debt, possibly due to their ability to generate sufficient internal funds.

Firm Leverage (FL) - Leverage generally has negative correlations with most variables, particularly with earnings quality (-0.463) and firm size (-0.417). This highlights that higher leverage is associated with poorer earnings quality and smaller firms. The key insights include Strong Positive Correlation: The most significant relationship is between audit firms (AF) and earnings quality (EQ), which is extremely strong (0.974). This suggests that external auditing plays a crucial role in ensuring high earnings quality. Moderate Positive Correlation: Both audit

committees (AC) and firm size (FS) are positively correlated with earnings quality, but the strength of these relationships is moderate. Larger firms and those with active audit committees tend to have better earnings quality, though the impact is not as strong as audit firms. Negative Impact of Leverage: Firm leverage (FL) is negatively correlated with both earnings' quality and firm size, indicating that highly leveraged firms are typically smaller and exhibit lower earnings quality. Profitability's Limited Role: Firm profitability (FP) shows only weak positive correlations with other variables, suggesting that while profitability does contribute to earnings quality, it is not as influential as audit-related factors or firm size. These insights align with expectations in corporate governance, where external audits and the size of the firm are key determinants of financial reporting quality. However, the negative impact of leverage highlights potential risks for firms with higher debt levels.

Furthermore, the regression results you provided offer several useful insights. The following is a detailed analysis of the key metrics: Regression Coefficients - Audit Firms (AF): The coefficient is 0.021750 with a robust standard error of 0.004791, indicating a positive and significant relationship between the presence of audit firms and earnings quality (EQ). The p-value (0.000) confirms the significance at any common significance level (1%, 5%, 10%). The 95% confidence interval suggests that the true coefficient lies between 0.0005857 and 0.0010207. Audit Committees (AC): The coefficient is 0.0120774 with a robust standard error of 0.003364, indicating a positive and significant relationship between audit committees and earnings quality. The p-value (0.000) supports strong evidence against the null hypothesis of no effect. This suggests that audit committees have a significant impact on improving earnings quality. Firm Size (FS): The coefficient for firm size is 0.03674, with a standard error of 0.013075. This is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.006, indicating that larger firms tend to have higher earnings quality. The confidence interval, between 0.0062708 and 0.0010771, also supports this positive effect. Firm Profitability (FP): The coefficient is 0.020086 with a standard error of 0.00589 and a p-value of 0.000, suggesting profitability positively influences earnings quality. The confidence interval is very tight, indicating robustness. Firm Leverage (FL): This variable is negative (-0.011372) but not statistically significant (p-value = 0.175). This suggests that firm leverage does not have a clear or reliable relationship with earnings quality based on this model.

Statistical significance and strength show that t-values: High t-values for AF (4.54), AC (3.59), FS (2.81), and FP (3.41) indicate strong statistical significance for these variables. However, FL has a low t-value (-1.36), further confirming that leverage is not statistically significant. P-values: All independent variables except for FL have p-values below 0.01, confirming strong evidence against the null hypothesis for AF, AC, FS, and FP. The p-value for FL (0.175) suggests that the variable is not significant at conventional levels. 95% Confidence Intervals: The confidence intervals for AF, AC, FS, and FP do not include zero, which strengthens the conclusion that these variables significantly affect earnings quality. On the other hand, the wide interval for FL includes zero, supporting its lack of statistical significance.

Model Fit - R-squared (R^2): The R^2 value of 0.2633 indicates that around 26.33% of the variability in earnings quality is explained by the model. While not very high, this R^2 suggests a moderate explanatory power. Model Fitness (p = 0.0093): The p-value for model fitness indicates that the model is overall statistically significant, but the relatively low R^2 suggests that there are other unobserved factors influencing earnings quality. Observations (Obs = 1530): With 1530 observations, the sample size is reasonably large, which generally contributes to the reliability of the regression estimates. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) - A VIF of 1.12 for the variables suggests no significant multicollinearity, meaning that the independent variables are not highly correlated, which ensures that the estimates are reliable. The heteroskedasticity test result (0.0000) suggests the presence of heteroskedasticity in the model. This is why robust standard errors have been used, which correct for the potential bias in the standard errors.

The key takeaways from these analyses include Audit Firms, Audit Committees, Firm Size, and Firm Profitability all positively and significantly influence earnings quality. Firm Leverage

does not appear to have a significant effect on earnings quality based on this model. The model explains 26.33% of the variance in earnings quality, indicating that other factors not included in the model might be influencing the outcome. There is no concern regarding multicollinearity, and the model is appropriately adjusted for heteroskedasticity. This analysis provides a good foundation but suggests the need for further exploration of other potential variables that could better explain earnings quality.

The statement provides a comprehensive analysis of the regression, correlation, and descriptive statistics related to earnings quality and its influencing factors. It systematically covers the relationships among key variables—Audit Firms (AF), Audit Committees (AC), Firm Size (FS), Firm Profitability (FP), and Firm Leverage (FL)—and how these factors impact earnings quality (EQ). The key insights include Earnings Quality (EQ) Trends: The dataset reflects relatively low earnings quality across the sample, with the analysis pointing toward governance and financial health as significant factors influencing EQ. Audit Firms and Committees: AF shows the strongest positive correlation with EQ, reinforcing the importance of external audits in enhancing earnings quality. AC also positively impacts EQ, but to a lesser extent, highlighting a potentially less direct but still valuable governance role. Financial Indicators: Firm size and profitability moderately contribute to better earnings quality. However, leverage negatively correlates with EQ, suggesting that high-debt firms are at greater risk of poor earnings quality. Regression Model Insights: The regression model finds statistically significant effects of AF, AC, FS, and FP on earnings quality, while leverage does not significantly affect EQ. The model explains around 26.33% of the variability in EQ, indicating moderate explanatory power but also the potential for other unobserved variables influencing outcomes. Practical Implications: The analysis underscores the need for audit firms and regulators to focus on firms' governance structures and financial leverage when assessing earnings quality.

Also, the analysis of the descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression results offers several implications for future research: Exploration of Additional Factors Influencing Earnings Quality. Unobserved Variables: With an R^2 value of 0.2633, only 26.33% of the variance in earnings quality is explained by the current model. Future research should explore other potential factors that may influence earnings quality. This could include Internal Corporate Governance Mechanisms: Variables such as board structure, management incentives, and shareholder rights may further explain earnings quality. Macroeconomic Variables: Economic conditions like inflation, interest rates, and industry-specific factors could play a role in earnings quality variations. Non-Financial Factors: Social responsibility, environmental performance, or corporate reputation might also impact earnings quality.

Non-Linear Relationships and Interactions: Interaction Effects: Future research could investigate whether interactions between variables (e.g., between firm size and audit firms or between leverage and profitability) affect earnings quality in ways not captured by simple linear regression. Exploring potential non-linear relationships between earnings quality and factors like firm size or profitability could yield more complex but informative patterns. Longitudinal Analysis: Temporal Effects: Conducting a longitudinal analysis could provide deeper insights into how earnings quality evolves over time and whether certain factors (like leverage or audit firm involvement) have delayed effects on earnings quality. Future research could examine if the relationships between governance factors (audit committees, audit firms) and earnings quality change over different periods or business cycles. Different Contexts and Firm Types: Cross-Country Comparisons: Investigating how earnings quality is influenced by audit firms, governance structures, and financial factors in different regulatory and economic environments would provide useful insights. Future studies could explore variations across countries, especially between developed and developing economies, where regulatory enforcement and corporate governance structures differ. Industry-Specific Research: Since firm size, profitability, and leverage vary significantly across industries, future research could explore how these factors affect earnings quality in specific sectors (e.g., technology,

manufacturing, or financial services). This would help identify industry-specific drivers of earnings quality.

Exploring the Role of Audit Committees in Greater Detail: Audit Committee Characteristics: While the analysis shows a positive correlation between audit committees and earnings quality, further research could explore the characteristics of audit committees that make them more effective, such as committee independence, expertise, and frequency of meetings. **Comparing Governance Mechanisms:** Future studies could compare the effectiveness of different governance mechanisms (e.g., board oversight, internal audits) with audit committees in enhancing earnings quality. **Alternative Measures of Earnings Quality: Different Definitions:** Future research might use alternative measures of earnings quality, such as accrual quality, earnings management, or real earnings management, to see whether the findings hold across different definitions of earnings quality. This would help validate the robustness of the current findings. **Qualitative Factors:** Examining qualitative aspects of financial reporting, such as transparency, disclosure quality, and the tone of management discussion, may offer a more holistic view of earnings quality.

Examining the Role of Leverage: Further Investigation of Leverage: Although leverage was found to be negatively correlated with earnings quality, it was not significant in the regression model. Future research could further investigate why leverage does not show a clear linear effect on earnings quality and whether thresholds of leverage exist, beyond which the impact becomes significant. **Behavioural Aspects of Corporate Governance: Behavioural Governance:** Incorporating behavioural economics into the study of corporate governance could uncover how decision-making biases (by boards, auditors, or managers) influence earnings quality. Future research could explore how management's risk tolerance or overconfidence impacts earnings quality, especially in firms with high leverage. **in conclusion,** these areas of future research can help deepen the understanding of earnings quality, governance mechanisms, and financial performance. The findings suggest that while audit-related variables, firm size, and profitability are critical, there are still unexplored variables and complex relationships that require further investigation to fully understand the determinants of earnings quality.

VIII. Conclusion

This study has examined the effect of corporate governance mechanisms and firm characteristics on the earnings quality of 153 publicly listed firms in Nigeria. The key findings summary includes Earnings Quality (EQ): Mean: 0.007 with a standard deviation of 0.008, indicating low earnings quality but relatively consistent across firms. Min/Max: Ranges from 0 to 0.063, suggesting minimal earnings manipulation. Audit Firms (AF): Mean: 0.466 with a standard deviation of 1.18, showing significant variability in audit firm engagement across firms. Min/Max: 0 to 5.355, reflecting that some firms utilize more prominent audit firms, while others do not. Audit Committees (AC): Mean: 0.316 with a standard deviation of 0.948, reflecting considerable differences in audit committee involvement. Min/Max: Ranges from 0.081 to 6.619, indicating varied governance through audit committees. Firm Size (FS): Mean: 9.276 (log scale) with a standard deviation of 0.43, showing stability in firm size. Min/Max: 8.119 to 10.098, reflecting a homogeneous group of larger firms. Firm Profitability (FP): Mean: 60.541 with a standard deviation of 10.61, indicating moderate variability in profitability. Min/Max: Ranges from 28.19 to 82.73, showing that some firms are significantly more profitable. Firm Leverage (FL): Mean: 0.929 with a standard deviation of 0.258, indicating moderate leverage across firms. Min/Max: 0.717 to 2.547, with some firms highly leveraged (debt greater than twice their equity).

Also, the correlation insights include EQ & Audit Firms (AF): Strong positive correlation (0.974), suggesting external auditing significantly improves earnings quality. EQ & Audit Committees (AC): Moderate positive correlation (0.349), indicating that active audit committees contribute to better earnings quality. EQ & Firm Size (FS): Moderate positive correlation (0.338), showing larger firms tend to have higher earnings quality. EQ & Firm

Profitability (FP): Weak positive correlation (0.202), suggesting only a slight improvement in earnings quality for more profitable firms. EQ & Firm Leverage (FL): Strong negative correlation (-0.463), indicating that highly leveraged firms generally exhibit lower earnings quality. Other notable relationships include AF & AC: Weak correlation (0.059) suggests that audit firms and committees act independently. Firm Size & Leverage: Strong negative correlation (-0.417), indicating larger firms tend to have lower leverage. Profitability & Leverage: Weak negative correlation (-0.212), showing more profitable firms have less debt. On regression results, Audit Firms (AF): Significant positive effect on earnings quality ($p < 0.01$). Audit Committees (AC): Also, significantly improves earnings quality ($p < 0.01$). Firm Size (FS): Positive and significant effect ($p < 0.01$). Firm Profitability (FP): Positive effect on earnings quality ($p < 0.01$). Firm Leverage (FL): Negative, but not statistically significant. On Model Fit: $R^2 = 0.2633$: The model explains 26.33% of the variability in earnings quality, suggesting other factors may play a role. No multicollinearity issues: $VIF = 1.12$. Model adjusted for heteroskedasticity using robust standard errors. In conclusion, the key drivers of earnings quality are audit firms, audit committees, firm size, and profitability. However, firm leverage does not significantly affect earnings quality, and additional factors beyond the model likely influence earnings quality.

The study provides several key contributions to the literature on earnings quality, corporate governance, and financial health. Here are the main contributions: Link Between Audit Firms and Earnings Quality: The strong positive correlation between audit firms (AF) and earnings quality (EQ) provides empirical evidence supporting the role of external auditors in enhancing the reliability of financial reports. This strengthens existing literature on the importance of external auditing in mitigating earnings manipulation and improving transparency, contributing to studies such as DeFond & Zhang (2014) that emphasize the role of audit quality in financial reporting integrity. The study highlights a moderate but significant positive relationship between audit committees (AC) and earnings quality, indicating that audit committees serve as an effective governance mechanism. This contribution aligns with prior literature, such as Klein (2002), which discusses the role of audit committees in curbing earnings management, adding empirical support to the governance literature that emphasizes internal oversight mechanisms. On Firm Size and Financial Reporting Quality: The positive and significant effect of firm size (FS) on earnings quality suggests that larger firms tend to report better-quality earnings, possibly due to greater scrutiny and more sophisticated governance structures. This finding corroborates existing research, such as Lang & Lundholm (1993), which suggests that larger firms have higher transparency due to stricter regulations and stakeholder demands. The contribution adds depth to the understanding of firm size as a determinant of financial reporting quality.

On Profitability's Limited Role in Earnings Quality: The weak but significant correlation between firm profitability (FP) and earnings quality suggests that profitability contributes less to earnings quality than audit and governance factors. This challenges the assumption that highly profitable firms inherently produce high-quality earnings. This nuanced contribution fills a gap in the literature, which has often assumed a strong link between profitability and reporting quality, offering a more measured view.

On the Negative Impact of Leverage on Earnings Quality: The strong negative correlation between firm leverage (FL) and earnings quality adds to the literature on financial structure by showing that higher levels of debt are associated with poorer financial reporting practices. This supports earlier findings by researchers like DeAngelo, DeAngelo, & Skinner (1994) and Jensen (1986), who argue that high leverage can increase the risk of financial distress, leading firms to manipulate earnings. The study extends this literature by empirically demonstrating the significance of leverage in corporate governance and earnings quality contexts.

On Governance Mechanisms in Corporate Finance: The findings highlight the importance of audit firms and committees as key governance mechanisms in influencing earnings quality, contributing to the literature on corporate governance. These insights reinforce prior studies by

Beasley (1996) and Carcello et al. (2002), which emphasize the importance of external and internal governance in curbing financial misreporting. The study advances this conversation by showing the differential effects of governance mechanisms.

Exploring New Variables for Earnings Quality: While the study finds that governance mechanisms and firm-specific financial variables like size, profitability, and leverage influence earnings quality, the modest explanatory power of the model ($R^2 = 26.33\%$) suggests the need for further exploration of additional factors. This contribution calls for future research to investigate non-traditional factors, such as corporate culture, managerial incentives, and external market conditions, which could enhance the understanding of earnings quality.

Empirical Evidence Supporting Corporate Governance Theories: The study provides empirical support for agency theory and resource dependence theory in the context of earnings quality, showing how external auditors and governance mechanisms reduce information asymmetry between managers and shareholders. By highlighting the critical role of audit firms and committees, the study adds to the corporate governance literature that seeks to reduce the conflict of interest between management and stakeholders, contributing to the broader governance and earnings quality debate. In sum, this study makes several important contributions by advancing the understanding of the relationships between audit mechanisms, financial structure, firm size, and earnings quality, while also identifying avenues for future research. These insights enhance the existing literature on earnings quality, corporate governance, and financial reporting.

How, on limitations, Sample Characteristics: The study focuses on a relatively homogeneous group of large firms (as indicated by the firm size distribution), which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Smaller firms, private companies, or firms from different industries or regions may exhibit different relationships between governance mechanisms and earnings quality. Future research could expand the scope to include more diverse firms to better understand how size and industry differences influence the dynamics of earnings quality.

Limited Scope of Variables: While the study incorporates important governance and financial variables (audit firms, audit committees, firm size, profitability, and leverage), the R^2 value of 26.33% suggests that other factors not included in the model also influence earnings quality. Future research could explore additional variables such as managerial incentives, ownership structure, corporate culture, or external market conditions, which may contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of earnings quality.

Cross-Sectional Nature of the Study: The analysis is based on cross-sectional data, which provides a snapshot of relationships between variables at a single point in time. This limits the ability to draw causal inferences or observe changes in earnings quality over time. Future research could employ longitudinal data to examine how changes in audit firm engagement, governance structures, or financial conditions affect earnings quality over multiple periods, allowing for a better understanding of causality.

Endogeneity Concerns: There may be endogeneity issues, such as reverse causality or omitted variable bias, particularly in the relationships between earnings quality and governance variables (e.g., audit firms and committees may improve earnings quality, but higher-quality firms might also attract better governance mechanisms). Future research could use advanced econometric techniques, such as instrumental variables or fixed-effects models, to address potential endogeneity and provide more robust causal interpretations.

Measurement Limitations: The study relies on aggregate measures, such as the number of audit firms and the presence of audit committees, without considering the quality, expertise, or reputation of these governance mechanisms. For instance, not all audit firms or committees may provide the same level of oversight or effectiveness. Future research could explore more granular measures of governance quality, such as audit firm reputation, auditor specialization, or audit committee expertise, to assess their specific impact on earnings quality.

Geographical and Regulatory Constraints: The findings may be influenced by specific legal, regulatory, and institutional frameworks relevant to the geographical region of the sample. The

role of audit firms and committees may differ across countries with varying regulations or corporate governance norms. Future research could explore cross-country comparisons or investigate the role of different regulatory environments in shaping the relationships between governance mechanisms and earnings quality. Exclusion of Non-Financial Factors: The study focuses on financial variables but does not account for non-financial factors, such as corporate social responsibility (CSR), environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance, or market competition, which could also affect earnings quality. Future research could integrate non-financial factors into the analysis to gain a more holistic understanding of what drives high-quality earnings in firms.

On Future Research Directions: **Expanding the Study to Different Types of Firms:** Future research could examine small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), privately held firms, or firms in emerging markets to explore whether the relationships between governance mechanisms and earnings quality differ across firm types and market environments. **Exploring the Role of Non-Traditional Governance Mechanisms:** The impact of non-traditional governance mechanisms such as board diversity, institutional investors, or the role of independent directors could be investigated in future research. This would expand the literature on how alternative governance structures influence financial reporting and earnings quality. **Longitudinal Studies:** Long-term studies examining how changes in governance structures (e.g., shifts in audit firm engagement or audit committee restructuring) affect earnings quality over time would provide valuable insights. This could help identify whether governance improvements lead to sustained earnings quality or whether these effects are temporary. **Impact of Economic Cycles on Earnings Quality:** Future research could explore how economic downturns or booms affect the relationship between governance mechanisms and earnings quality. For example, firms may be more prone to earnings manipulation during periods of financial distress, which could alter the effectiveness of audit mechanisms. **Interaction Effects Between Variables:** Exploring potential interaction effects between variables, such as the combined impact of audit firms and audit committees or the interplay between profitability and leverage, could reveal more complex dynamics affecting earnings quality. This could be done through moderated or mediated regression models. **Advanced Econometric Techniques:** Future studies could employ advanced econometric methods, such as structural equation modeling (SEM) or difference-in-differences (DID) analysis, to better capture complex relationships and address potential endogeneity issues in the model.

Investigating Behavioral and Psychological Factors: Behavioral aspects such as managerial decision-making biases, risk preferences, or incentive structures could be studied to understand how internal factors influence earnings manipulation and reporting quality. This could open new areas in the intersection of behavioral economics and corporate governance. **Incorporating ESG Factors:** As the importance of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors grows in corporate evaluations, future research could investigate how these non-financial aspects correlate with earnings quality, potentially revealing new drivers of high-quality financial reporting. By addressing these limitations and exploring these future research avenues, subsequent studies can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing earnings quality and deepen insights into corporate governance's role in financial reporting practices.

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Acknowledgments

We appreciate the contributions of the journal editors and two anonymous reviewers. We also appreciate the contributions of our postgraduate students, particularly concerning data collection and the 2023 Conference participants at the Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna

Conflict of Interest

None

Funding

None

Disclaimer

The views expressed herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Journal of Financial Economics and Accounting Editorial Board members.

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